

The use of the performance measures of queuing model to optimize profit in a Cloud Computing environment

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Abstract— Cloud computing is a developed technology which can transform the manner how traditional companies work. It becomes crucial in the IT industry. In addition, Cloud computing enables users to utilize computing resources distantly in a pay-per-use pattern. However, there are some of the critical problems in cloud computing environments among which are below-average price cut in the queue length, server use rate, answer time, and waiting time. Accordingly, so as to tackle aforesaid issues, this paper pays closer attention to the queuing model approach for the purpose of ameliorating QoS in cloud computing and optimizing resources effectively in order to decrease execution time and cost and to obtain a better performance. Our model is employed in the case that there are two or more servers working in parallel, separately with an arrival process which is distributed according to a Poisson law and a service process corresponding to an exponential law. It is by the same token supposed that the system studied is in a stable state. After that, the numerical results are presented. Ultimately, we treated the optimization of cost so as to making the maximum profit in the cloud computing environment.

Keywords- *Cloud computing environments; Queuing model; Quality of service (QoS); Profit optimization*

I. INTRODUCTION

During the last years, the people's business day and way of life have exceedingly transformed with the fast evolution and broad implementation of cloud computing technology. A considerable advance in cloud computing adoption is expected. The global cloud computing market range is predicted to increase from USD 371.4 billion in 2020 to USD 832.1 billion by 2025, at a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 17.5% in the course of the prediction duration [1,2]. It could be implemented in several domains by way of example IoT

applications, data storage and data analysis [3]. It furnishes diverse capabilities through the internet to customers who don't want to invest in the computing architecture. A cloud ecosystem is composed generally of three main elements: Cloud consumer, Cloud provider and Cloud services. Cloud Consumer uses the cloud services provisioned by the Cloud provider [4]. Software as a Service (SaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS) and Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) are some of the services furnished by the Cloud supplier [5,6]. With a view to serve the purpose of the customers' demands, the Cloud service supplier has to handle the resources. SaaS provides services to the clients via the Internet and these furnished cloud applications are accessible through dependent user applications like web navigators. Web-mail, social media, video-sharing and word processing sites are some of these service cloud applications offered by SaaS [7]. PaaS is an application platform over which custom applications and services can be deployed. Infrastructure as a service is a physical infrastructure that is abstracted to provide processing power, storage network bandwidth and other fundamental computing resources which allow users to deploy and run their applications and software [8,9].

The vendor of cloud services offers needed resources by way of scalable virtual machines hired to clients at a nominal fee on assured levels of QoS as approved in registered service level agreement (SLA) between the two participants. Schematically, for both supplier and customer, there is an immediate impact on the agreeable quality of service based on efficacy, performance, due time, price, profit, etc.[10, 11], when a massive number of client tasks demanding service come at cloud service supplier. In order to maintain QoS in accordance with SLA taking into consideration supplier's sales

and other associated metrics it is important to opt for an efficacious system model such as the queuing model [12].

Figure 1. The queuing theory illustration

Queues are formed when customers arrive randomly for service or more often when arrivals are in groups or when service times are particularly long [13]. However, when we talk about waiting, we often think of people. Fig. 1 shows the queuing theory.

Typically, customers see an activity with no added value waiting and, if they wait too long, they associate this waste of time with poor quality of service. To avoid these situations, the majority of companies have implemented continuous improvement processes whose ultimate goal is to eliminate all forms of waste, including waiting. All of these examples illustrate the importance of queuing analysis.

Queues always give a negative image of the offered quality of service and possibly poor customer satisfaction. In this situation, enterprises will tend to identify a compromise between the cost associated with service capacity and the cost of waiting for customers.

The queuing analysis objective is to decrease the sum of the two costs: the cost of waiting for clients and the service cost.

In a system, queuing concept is extremely essential for commanding. Queuing concept is the mathematical analysis of queue length and waiting time [14,15,16].

The queuing analysis is conceived in a manner that clients do not be obliged to wait for services for a long time.

In fact, a queuing theory plays a great crucial function in how to meet Cloud computing clients QoS demands and use the Cloud resources effectively in an inexpensive manner. Commonly, the Cloud computing resources users constantly expect which Cloud computing resource can meet their QoS demands for computing (for example the due time of the work accomplished, the computing capacity etc.), how much money they must pay for the Cloud Computing resources. While, the vendors of Cloud computing services consider in what way they can reach the greatest benefits by furnishing resources, in addition to satisfy the customers QoS demands [17].

The current paper aims attention at the queuing model approach for the purpose of ameliorating QoS in Cloud computing by using performance measures for optimization.

The rest of this paper is systematized along these lines. Section 2 examines the related work. Section 3 exhibits the queuing model deals with the numerical result. Section 4 represents the queuing optimization. After all, we finalize our work in Section 5.

II. RELATED WORK

Within this present section, we review the relevant publications in the direction of our work.

The author of [17] brings up a differentiated service job scheduling system for a Cloud computing technology. He creates the corresponding non pre-emptive priority $M/G/1$ queuing model for this system through evaluating the differential QoS demands of clients' tasks. This corresponding algorithm is making in order to obtain the estimated optimistic value of service to every single task by means of diverse order of priorities.

Fig. 2 presents the arrival and departure in a single server system $M/M/1$ queuing model [14].

In some studies [18,19], queuing concept has been employed to study or maximize considerations namely load sharing, benefit control, and power allocating [20].

The authors of [18] exhibited an energy proportional pattern that processes a server as a $M/G/1$ queuing model like a procedure in order to enhance performance effectiveness.

In this study [22], through employing a cloud center pattern like the classic open network, the reply delivery time was received, based on the premise that the service time and the time between two arrivals are exponential. The link between the high number of jobs, the lower service resources, and the maximum level of service was established by applying the reply delivery time.

With a view to study the resource allocation difficulties in each of two single-class service and multiple-class service situations, the authors of [23] utilize the queuing theory. They enhance the resource allocation to reduce the average response time or diminish the resource expense in both situations.

Figure 2. The illustration of $M/M/1$ queuing model [14]

In [24], they built the M/M/1 queuing model predicting method in order to maintain improved response time and minor energy consumption.

In [25], they used M/M/c queuing system and Erlang's model so as to decrease waiting time in cloud computing. The outcomes were acted on various values of service rate, arrival rate and number of servers.

Within this article [26], the authors studied the issue of resource delivery in cloud computing. They have designed a cloud center applying the M/M/C/C queuing model regarding various priority levels so as to sustain decision taking in the matter of resource distribution for a cloud service supplier at the time that various customers discussed diverse service level agreements.

The authors within [27] employed a M/G/m/m+r queuing model in order to measure a cloud computing center and attained an absolute probability delivery of response time and number of jobs in the system.

On the basis of these studies, It is realized that by employing the queuing concept regarding the study of performance and exams has been analyzed in cloud computing. However, on the subject of performance measures for profit maximization, more studies are necessary. In addition, the study that handles all the criterion of QoS contemporaneously according to prevailing studies does not exist. Within this present paper, we utilize the M/M/m queuing model approach with the aim of enhancing QoS in Cloud computing through performance measures for optimization.

III. THE M/M/M QUEUING MODEL

There exist a large number of consumers, in a cloud computing environment, who use the services.

So such a model exists when there are two or more servers working in parallel, independently. The following assumptions must first be verified:

- The arrival process is distributed according to a Poisson law and the service process according to an exponential law.
- The average service rate is the same for all servers.
- Customers are processed on a first-come, first-served basis (FCFS service discipline). FCFS is a queuing order where the tasks which first come in the queuing will be served first. This kind of service discipline provides a proficiency of the system.

It is also assumed that the system studied is in a permanent (stationary) state, meaning that arrival and service rates are stable.

The M/M/m queuing model is a multiple server system. It is otherwise known as mutiserver queue where servers furnish facilities to the clients [14, 21].

To facilitate the use of the model, Table 1 presents the symbols and terminology used.

TABLE I. SYMBOL SIGNIFICANCE

Symbol	Significance
λ	Customer Arrival Rate
μ	Service rate
ρ	Utilization rate of the system
L_f	Average number of clients in the queue (clients waiting to be served)
L	Average number of clients in the system (clients waiting and clients being served)
$1/\lambda$	Service time
W_f	Mean waiting time in the queue
W	Mean waiting time in system(Queue Wait Time, plus Service Time or System Stay Time)
$p(0)$	Probability that there is zero unit (client) in the system
$p(n)$	Probability of n units (clients) in the system
m	Number of servers

There are some basic relations that determine the desired performance measures with a few key values. Arrival rate λ and service rate μ must be expressed in the same unit of measure. The main relations are presented below:

Utilization rate of the system:

$$\rho = \frac{\lambda}{m\mu} \quad (1)$$

It represents the ratio of demand (measured by the rate of arrival, λ) to service capacity (product of the number of servers m by the rate of service, μ).

Average number of clients being served:

$$\rho = \lambda/\mu \quad (2)$$

Average number of clients in the queue:

L_f is obtained from a table or the appropriate formula, depending on the model in question. L_f is the key element used to determine other system performance measures, such as the average number of customers in the system, the mean time spent in the queue and the mean time spent in the system. Therefore, when resolving queuing issues, the first performance measure to consider is L_f .

Number of customers in the system:

$$L = L_f + \rho \quad (3)$$

Mean waiting time in the queue:

$$W_f = L_f / \lambda \quad (4)$$

Mean waiting time in system:

$$W = W_f + 1/\mu = L/\lambda \quad (5)$$

Note: For this model, the system usage rate should be less than 1 ($\lambda < m\mu$). On the other hand, this model applies only to systems that are not congested. There is no use in analyzing systems in which $\lambda > m\mu$, as it is obvious that in such cases they are congested.

- There are five measurement tools or indices to assess the performance of an existing system of producing services. These measures are:
- The average number of clients waiting in line or in the system (see Fig.1).
- The average waiting time in the queue and in the system.
- The usage rate of the system, which is the percentage of capacity used.
- The cost associated with the level of service (capacity) put in place.
- The probability of a potential client waiting to be served.

TABLE II. VALUES OF L_f AND $p(0)$

λ/μ	m	L_f	$p(0)$	λ/μ	m	L_f	$p(0)$	λ/μ	m	L_f	$p(0)$
0,15	1	0,026	,850	0,85	1	4,817	,150	1,7	2	4,426	,081
	2	0,001	,860		2	0,187	,404		3	0,409	,166
0,20	1	0,050	,800		3	0,024	,425		4	0,080	,180
	2	0,002	,818		4	0,003	,427		5	0,017	,182
0,25	1	0,083	,750	0,90	1	8,100	,100	1,8	2	7,674	,053
	2	0,004	,778		2	0,229	,379		3	0,532	,146
0,30	1	0,129	,700		3	0,030	,403		4	0,105	,162
	2	0,007	,739		4	0,004	,406		5	0,023	,165
0,35	1	0,188	,650	0,95	1	18,050	,050	1,9	2	17,587	,026
	2	0,011	,702		2	0,277	,356		3	0,688	,128
0,40	1	0,267	,600		3	0,037	,383		4	0,136	,145
	2	0,017	,667		4	0,005	,386		5	0,030	,149
0,45	1	0,368	,550	1,0	2	0,333	,333	2,0	3	0,889	,111
	2	0,024	,633		3	0,045	,364		4	0,174	,130
	3	0,002	,637		4	0,007	,367		5	0,040	,134
0,50	1	0,500	,500	1,1	2	0,477	,290	2,1	3	1,149	,096
	2	0,033	,600		3	0,066	,327		4	0,220	,117
	3	0,003	,606		4	0,011	,367		5	0,052	,121
0,55	1	0,672	,450	1,2	2	0,675	,250	2,2	3	1,491	,081
	2	0,045	,569		3	0,094	,294		4	0,277	,105
	3	0,004	,576		4	0,016	,300		5	0,066	,109
0,60	1	0,900	,400	1,3	2	0,951	,212	2,3	3	1,951	,068
	2	0,059	,538		3	0,130	,264		4	0,346	,093
	3	0,006	,548		4	0,023	,271		5	0,084	,099
0,65	1	1,207	,350	1,4	2	1,345	,176	2,4	3	2,589	,056
	2	0,077	,509		3	0,177	,236		4	0,431	,083
	3	0,008	,521		4	0,032	,245		5	0,105	,089
0,70	1	1,633	,300	1,5	2	1,929	,143	2,5	3	3,511	,045
	2	0,098	,481		3	0,237	,211		4	0,533	,074
	3	0,011	,495		4	0,045	,221		5	0,130	,080
0,75	1	2,250	,250	1,6	2	2,844	,111	2,6	3	4,933	,035
	2	0,123	,455		3	0,313	,187		4	0,658	,065
	3	0,015	,471		4	0,060	,199		5	0,161	,072
0,80	1	3,200	,200	1,7	2	4,012	,082	2,7	3	7,354	,025
	2	0,152	,429		3	0,012	,201		4	0,811	,057
	3	0,019	,447		4	0,019	,201		5	0,198	,065
					5	0,028	,029		6	0,053	,067
					6	0,007	,030		7	0,014	,067
					7	0,007	,030		8	0,003	,033
					8	0,019	,027		9	0,002	,015
					9	0,008	,027		10	0,009	,015
					10	0,007	,030		11	0,009	,015
					12	0,007	,030		13	0,009	,015
					14	0,007	,030		15	0,009	,015
					16	0,007	,030		17	0,009	,015
					18	0,007	,030		19	0,009	,015
					20	0,007	,030		21	0,009	,015
					22	0,007	,030		23	0,009	,015
					24	0,007	,030		25	0,009	,015
					26	0,007	,030		27	0,009	,015
					28	0,007	,030		29	0,009	,015
					30	0,007	,030		31	0,009	,015
					32	0,007	,030		33	0,009	,015
					34	0,007	,030		35	0,009	,015
					36	0,007	,030		37	0,009	,015
					38	0,007	,030		39	0,009	,015
					40	0,007	,030		41	0,009	,015
					42	0,007	,030		43	0,009	,015
					44	0,007	,030		45	0,009	,015
					46	0,007	,030		47	0,009	,015
					48	0,007	,030		49	0,009	,015
					50	0,007	,030		51	0,009	,015
					52	0,007	,030		53	0,009	,015
					54	0,007	,030		55	0,009	,015
					56	0,007	,030		57	0,009	,015
					58	0,007	,030		59	0,009	,015
					60	0,007	,030		61	0,009	,015
					62	0,007	,030		63	0,009	,015
					64	0,007	,030		65	0,009	,015
					66	0,007	,030		67	0,009	,015
					68	0,007	,030		69	0,009	,015
					70	0,007	,030		71	0,009	,015
					72	0,007	,030		73	0,009	,015
					74	0,007	,030		75	0,009	,015
					76	0,007	,030		77	0,009	,015
					78	0,007	,030		79	0,009	,015
					80	0,007	,030		81	0,009	,015
					82	0,007	,030		83	0,009	,015
					84	0,007	,030		85	0,009	,015
					86	0,007	,030		87	0,009	,015
					88	0,007	,030		89	0,009	,015
					90	0,007	,030		91	0,009	,015
					92	0,007	,030		93	0,009	,015
					94	0,007	,030		95	0,009	,015
					96	0,007	,030		97	0,009	,015
					98	0,007	,030		99	0,009	,015
					100	0,007	,030		101	0,009	,015

Among these five measurement tools, the rate of use of the system requires some clarification. It reflects the extent of server occupancy rather than inactivity.

It is logical to think that a good management of resources implies a utilization rate of 100%. However, increasing the utilization rate increases both the number of clients waiting and the average waiting time.

In fact, these two measures increase indefinitely when the utilization rate approaches 100%. If all the servers are busy, it is certain that the potential customers who arrive will wait. This implies that under normal operating conditions, a 100% utilization rate is unrealistic. Therefore, the system must be optimized in the manner that the sum of the service and waiting costs is minimal, as shown in Fig. 3.

The formulae for calculating the performance measures of this model are as follows:

$$L_f = \frac{\lambda\mu \left(\frac{\lambda}{\mu}\right)^m}{(m-1)!(m\mu-\lambda)^2} p(0) \tag{6}$$

$$p(0) = \left[\sum_{n=0}^{m-1} \frac{\left(\frac{\lambda}{\mu}\right)^n}{n!} + \frac{\left(\frac{\lambda}{\mu}\right)^m}{m! \left(1 - \frac{\lambda}{m\mu}\right)} \right]^{-1} \tag{7}$$

We denote the notation W_a by the mean waiting time for a prospect client not served immediately.

$$W_a = 1/(m\mu - \lambda) \tag{8}$$

We designate the notation P_w by the probability of a potential client waiting to be served.

$$P_w = W_f/W_a \tag{9}$$

Example: The Table 2 gives the values of L_f and $p(0)$ for different values of λ/μ and m .

To use the Table 2, we calculate at first the value of λ/μ (rounded to decimal places as in the table), then we simply read the values L_f and $p(0)$ corresponding to the appropriate number of servers, m . For example, if $\lambda/\mu = 0.50$ and $m = 2$, we can read: $L_f = 0,033$ and $p(0) = 0,600$.

λ/μ	m	L_f	$p(0)$	λ/μ	m	L_f	$p(0)$	λ/μ	m	L_f	$p(0)$
4.8	5	21,641	,002	5.3	6	5,303	,003	5.7	6	16,446	,001
	6	2,071	,006		7	1,249	,004		7	2,264	,002
	7	0,607	,008		8	0,422	,005		8	0,721	,003
	8	0,209	,008		9	0,155	,005		9	0,266	,003
	9	0,074	,008		10	0,057	,005		10	0,102	,003
	10	0,026	,008		11	0,021	,005		11	0,038	,003
4.9	5	46,566	,001		12	0,007	,005		12	0,014	,003
	6	2,459	,005		12	0,007	,005				
	7	0,702	,007	5.4	7	1,444	,004	5.8	6	26,373	,001
	8	0,242	,007		8	0,483	,004		7	2,648	,002
	9	0,087	,007		9	0,178	,004		8	0,823	,003
	10	0,031	,007		10	0,066	,004		9	0,303	,003
	11	0,011	,077		11	0,024	,005		10	0,116	,003
5.0	6	2,938	,005		12	0,009	,005		11	0,044	,003
	7	0,810	,006	5.5	6	8,590	,002	5.9	6	56,300	,000
	8	0,279	,006		7	1,674	,003		7	3,113	,002
	9	0,101	,007		8	0,553	,004		8	0,939	,002
	10	0,036	,007		9	0,204	,004		9	0,345	,003
	11	0,013	,007		10	0,077	,004		10	0,133	,003
5.1	6	3,536	,004		11	0,028	,004				
	7	0,936	,005		12	0,010	,004				
	8	0,321	,006	5.6	6	11,519	,001				
	9	0,117	,006		7	1,944	,003				
	10	0,042	,006		8	0,631	,003				
	11	0,015	,006		9	0,233	,004				
5.2	6	4,301	,003		10	0,088	,004				
	7	1,081	,005		11	0,033	,004				
	8	0,368	,005		12	0,012	,004				
	9	0,135	,005								
	10	0,049	,005								
	11	0,017	,006								

Figure 3. Graph representing the optimal level of service

When service capacity increases, the cost of service increases, but the number of clients waiting and the wait time tends to decrease, so the wait costs decrease. Fig. 3 illustrates this concept well; the total cost is represented on the graph by a U-shaped curve.

Remark: Note that when optimizing, the wait and service costs are estimates, so the optimal solution obtained may not be true. The calculation of total cost to the nearest cent or even to the nearest dollar suggests a high degree of precision, which is not supported by the cost estimates. This is also complicated by the fact that the approximations of arrival and service rates by Poisson and exponential distributions can be false.

Another solution would be to estimate the cost per interval (for example, the cost of waiting for customers would be between \$40 and \$50 per hour). In this case, the total cost for each of the limits should be calculated to verify if the optimal solution is affected. If so, the manager will have to decide whether it is necessary to make additional efforts to obtain more precision in the cost estimates or simply choose one of the two optimal solutions obtained. The manager will likely choose the latter approach if the variations in total cost for different capacity levels are minimal compared to the optimal solutions obtained.

Cloud computing has fascinated a growing number of persons and firms to utilize it. Subsequently, it became increasingly considerable to apply it more efficiently and profitably.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper devotes more attention to the queuing model approach to handle the problem of optimum multiserver structure for optimizing profit in the cloud computing environment and to evaluate the performance of services. Among the criteria which are taken in account by our queuing model in order to satisfy the cloud computing users, we have the quality of a service and the service level agreement.

In the table above, we have numerical results using the M/M/m queuing model. Based on queuing model, it has been indicated the average number of clients being served, the number of servers, average number of clients in the queue, and the probability that there is zero client in the system as λ/μ , m , L_f , and $p(0)$ respectively.

IV. QUEUE OPTIMIZATION

To design a system, the cost associated with the level of service (service capacity) is calculated and compared with the cost of waiting for customers (cost incurred by the business due to the expectation of customers in the system). The optimal service capacity (usually the number of servers working in parallel) is the one that reduces the total cost of waiting management. This total cost is the sum of the waiting cost of the customers and the cost of the service capacity.

The objective is therefore to minimize the total cost:

$$C_T = \text{waiting cost } (C_w) + \text{service cost } (C_s)$$

The optimization approach is to calculate the total cost of the system according to different values corresponding to the number of servers. After a number of iterations, the capacity is established that minimizes the total cost. Since the curve representing the total cost is U-shaped, increasing the number of servers will cause the total cost to decrease to the minimum. From there, increasing the capacity will instead lead to an increase in the total cost. So that's where the optimal capacity is.

The cost of waiting is calculated based on the average number of clients in the system. It may not be intuitively obvious, but it would be tempting to look at the average wait time in the system.

Our model is applied when there are two or more servers working in parallel, autonomously with an arrival process which is distributed according to a Poisson law and a service process corresponding to an exponential law. The mean service rate is as well the same for all servers and the users are treated on a first-come, first-served principle (FCFS service discipline). It is by the same token presumed that the system analyzed is in a permanent state, this indicates that arrival and service rates are stable. Then, the numerical results are given. Lastly, we treated the optimization of cost with the intention of making the maximum profit in the cloud computing environment.

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